

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

Scientific and Academy Journal

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.329

Vol. (47/2)–SPECIAL ISSUE OCTOBER-2025

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**1-International Security Cooperation of
Ukraine in The Face of The Russian-
Ukrainian War: Factors of Historical and
Legal Aspects. By Yurii Rusnak and others.
p. 10.**

CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH-DENMARK

AALBORG ACADEMY OF SCIENCES – DENMARK

<http://journal-law.com/>

journallaw1@yahoo.co

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

Vol. 47-2-Special Issue-Ukraine-October2025

First edition 2011

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

SCIENTIFIC AND ACADEMY JOURNAL

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.701

VOL. (47/2) SPECIAL ISSUE OCTOBER 2025

FIRST EDITION 2011

SPECIAL ISSUE

LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE

A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE

PREPARED

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
FACULTY OF LAW - ACADEMY OF THE AALBORG – DENMARK**

<http://journal-law.com/>

journallaw1@yahoo.co

Chief in Editor Prof. SUHAIL H. AL-FATLAW

General Supervisor-Prof. TALAL ALNADAW

Secretary of the Editorial Board-Prof. SALEH AL-TAI

Editorial Board

- 1- Prof. HOSSAM GHARABAWI: University of Baghdad – Iraq
- 2- Prof. ADEL AL ALI -University of Al - Isra University- Jordan.
- 3- Prof. YURIY PYVOVAR. Department of Constitutional and Administrative Law -National Aviation University, Ukraine.
- 4- Prof. JAMIL MUSAB-University of Baghdad – Iraq.
- 5- Prof. E SAHIB OBEID AL – FATAWI-Amman National University – Jordan.
- 6- Prof. MUSLEH HASSAN AL – HADITHI-Al-Rashid University, Iraq.
- 7- Dr. Nguyen Binh An (B. An Nguyen) Law Faculty, Binh Duong University- Vietnam
- 8- Prof. AAD ALI AL-KAISSI -University of Sharjah-UAE.
- 9-PROF. ASHJAN AL-ZUHAIRY
Al-Qasim University, College of Sharia and Islamic Studies- Saudi Arabia-Systems Department
- 10-- Prof. ACHOUR FTIMA -Dean of the Faculty of Law – Algeria.
- 11- Dr. OROOBA JABAR ABDEL HUSSEIN,
DIRECTOR of the Journal's Department

ADVISERS

Prof. Noman Al-Khatib, President of the University of Jordan

Pro. Shafiq al-Samarrai - University President-Belgium

Prof. Emad Rabee Vice President of Jerash University-Jordan

Prof. Ahmed Abu Shanab - Amman Arab University- Jordan

Prof. Mohammed Wsal- Dean of the Faculty of Law-Syria

Prof. Ali Al_husenawe- Dean of the Faculty of Law-Iraq

Prof. Mohamed Hossam- Dean of the Faculty of Law-Oman

**Prof. Ahmed Hawamdeh- Dean of the Faculty of Law- Jerash University
- Jordan**

Dr. Abderrahman Alarman -Dean of the Law Faculty-Jordan

Prof. Mohamed About Ela- Academy-Egypt

Prof. Asaid Mostafa Aboalker-Academy-Eyjpt

Prof. Khalil Elias Murad -Denmark

Prof. Dr. Mustafa Eчек- Academy-Turkey

Prof. Ahmed Fedaioglu Academy-Turkey

Prof. Karim Harzallah- Academy- Algeria

Prof. Aiser Khalil Al-Obidi- Baghdad university Iraq

Prof. Amrouche elhoucine Faculty of Law and Political Science -Yahiya

Fares University-Medea –Algeria

Dr. Murtada Abdullah Khairi- Academy-Sudan

Rosi Topham- Academy-UK

The Journal certified by:

 ESCI	
<p>The Journal of Law and Political Sciences is published by the Law and Political Research Center which is accredited by CVR - Det Centrale Virksomhedsregister-Denmark</p>	 cvr virk
<p>Accredited by the Faculty of Law - Aalborg Academy of Sciences –Denmark</p>	
<p>Islamic Word Science citation Center</p>	
<p>INTERNATIONAL Scientific Indexing</p>	<p>QUALITY IMPACT VALUE 2.329</p>
 TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL	<p>QUALITY IMPACT VALUE 7.234</p>

Published Terms in the journal:

1. Number of pages of no more than 40 pages. 14 × 21 cm;
2. Subject of research in the Law and political and Islamic law;
3. Researcher must use scientific sources, or documents depends referred to in accordance with the scientific bases used in scientific research;
4. The research includes an abstract of no more than 150 words.
5. The research includes keyword.
6. The introduction shall include the importance of research and the research problem. The introduction shall not exceed two pages.
7. The research referred on two experts, to ensure compliance with the terms of the researcher scientific research;
8. Written in the footnote in the bottom of the page and printed electronically.
9. The researcher shall have a PhD in law, or political science or Islamic law.
10. Research written in English, French or Arabic language.
11. The researcher is responsible for the views expressed in his research.
12. Research is sent by e-mail to the head of the editorial board.
13. At the end of the research conclusion includes the pleadings and recommendations.
14. List of sources by alphabet at the end of research.
15. The research may not be published in another journal, or in a book.

International Journal Evaluation

 website stats and valuation			

 INTERNATIONAL
Scientific Indexing
Fresh Ideas for Growing your Citations

Certificate

This is to certify that **Journal of Law and Political Science** is indexed in International Scientific Indexing (ISI). The Journal has Impact Factor Value of **2.329** based on International Citation Report (ICR) for the year **2022-2023**. The URL for journal on our server is <https://isindexing.com/isi/journaldetails.php?id=4032>

Editor ICR Team (ISI) International Scientific Indexing (ISI)

Contents of Vol. No. (47/2) of Issue October-2025

- 1- International Security Cooperation of Ukraine in The Face of The Russian-Ukrainian War: Factors of Historical and Legal Aspects. By Yurii Rusnak and others. p. 10.**
- 2- Global Strategic Rivalry and the Secure Architecture: Nato's Influence on The Formation of The International Peace, By Yevhenii Taran. and others. p. 30.**
- 3- Multipolarity of the Global Space: Strategic Understanding of Geopolitical Trends. By Viacheslav Kolotov and others. p. 55.**
- 4- Mechanisms for Restoring Violated Rights to Intellectual Products: Law Enforcement Difficulties in Ukraine. By Viktoriia Kobko-Odarii and others. p. 82.**
- 5- Civic Engagement as a Driver of Political Change in Post-Totalitarian States. Vitalii Kostenko and others. p. 104.**
- 6- International Humanitarian Law Implications During the War in Ukraine: Problems and Violations. By Oleksandr Khomenko and others. p. 123.**
- 7- Russian-Ukrainian War's Geopolitical Consequences for Eastern Europe. By Vira Kazymir and others. p. 138.**
- 8- Constitutional Rights and Freedoms of Citizens: Problems of Protection And Implementation In Ukraine. By Denys Chyzhov . And others. P. 154.**
- 9- Criminal Liability for Economic Crimes: Issues of Legal Qualification And Application In Practice. By Volodymyr Myslyvyy and others. p. 176.**
- 10- The Dynamics of Public-Private Interaction in Advancing Sustainable Development Through Investment Strategies and Administration. By Myroslav Buryk and others. p. 198.**
- 11- Cooperation of Governmental Institutions And Advocacy Associations Within the Framework of The Fundamental Freedoms: Conceptual Perspective. By Olena Bondarchuk- Ladna and others. p. 228.**
- 12- The Issue of Criminal Liability for Corruption Crimes in The Context of Legal Modernization. By Anfisa Serhiienko and others. p. 250.**
- 13- Anti-Corruption Policy and Its Administration in Public Administration: Theoretical Foundations and Practical Aspects of the Legal Framework. By Oleksii Vasyliiev and others. p. 276.**
- 14- Electoral Behavioral Models in Sweden and Norway: A Psychopolitical Perspective. By Viktor Melnyk and others. p. 299.**
- 15- The Evolution of Legal Frameworks in Lithuanian State Formation: Historical Perspectives -and The Impact of European Integration. By Lesia Kotsur and others. p. 325.**
- 16- Public Debt and Public Debt Administration Under Martial Law in the Process of Post-War Reconstruction, By Serhii Petrukha and others. p. 341.**
- 17- Global Economic Interaction as a Factor of Innovative Progress in Countries with A Transformational Model of Growth. By Yevhenii Kostyk and others. p. 372,**

(1)

**INTERNATIONAL SECURITY COOPERATION
OF UKRAINE IN THE FACE OF THE RUSSIAN-
UKRAINIAN WAR: FACTORS OF HISTORICAL
AND LEGAL ASPECTS**

Receipt 1/8/2025

Approval 18/9/2025

Publishing October 2025

YURII RUSNAK

Candidate of Legal Sciences, Senior Researcher, Honored Lawyer of Ukraine, Deputy Head of the Center, Head of the Research Department for Resource Provision in the field of Defense and Military Construction, The Centre for Military and Strategic Studies, The National Defence University of Ukraine, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1418-5793>

rusnakui@ukr.net

DMYTRO RUSNAK

PhD, Senior Researcher, Scientific Research Department for the Implementation of Standards of Scientific Integrity, Scientific Center for the Prevention of Corruption in the Field of Security and Defense, National Defence University of Ukraine, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8388-8786>

kirpich2008@ukr.net

LIUDMYLA PRYPOLOVA

Candidate of Legal Sciences, Senior Researcher, Chief of the Research Division of Legal Problems in the Field of International Cooperation, Research Department for Resource Provision in the Field of Defense and Military Construction, Centre for Military and Strategic Studies, National Defence University of Ukraine, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8429-1866>

mila.prypolova@ukr.net

YURII DIDOVETS

Postgraduate Student, Faculty of Decorative and Applied Arts in Mykhailo Boychuk Kyiv State Academy of Decorative Applied Arts and Design, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1440-6944>

aa5222bp@gmail.com

YULIIA STUZHUK

Research Fellow, Research Department of Legal Issues in the Sphere of International Cooperation, Research Directorate of Resource Support Issues in the Military Sphere, Defense, and Military Construction of the Center for Military-Strategic Studies, Center for Military-Strategic Studies, National Defence University of Ukraine, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8017-9259>

juliastuzhuk97@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The relevance of the study is determined by the need for a systematic analysis of the evolution of Ukraine's international security cooperation in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. The article examines the development of Ukraine's international security cooperation in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war, focusing on the legal, institutional and strategic aspects of interaction with international partners. The research methodology involved the use of an interdisciplinary approach, combining the political, legal, historical, international and security aspects of the studied issues. The key stages of the transformation of Ukraine's security policy since 2014, when after the Revolution of Dignity and the beginning of the Russian Federation's aggression, a radical revision of defense strategies and mechanisms of international cooperation took place, are identified. The role and influence of international organizations such as NATO and the European Union in providing military, financial and political support to Ukraine is examined. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of legal acts regulating international military cooperation, including strategic defense agreements, technical arrangements, and military cooperation programs. The analysis made it possible to identify the main directions of Ukraine's integration into the international security system, including reforming the Armed Forces, implementing NATO standards, strengthening cybersecurity, and expanding military-technical cooperation. Prospects for further research are focused on assessing the effectiveness of the implemented reforms, developing mechanisms for institutional strengthening of the defense sector, and forecasting Ukraine's further integration into the Euro-Atlantic security space.

Keywords: international security cooperation, national security, NATO, European Union, military-technical cooperation, strategic agreements, cybersecurity, defense reform.

1- INTRODUCTION

The perpetual transformation of socio-humanitarian constellations necessitates a rigorous reassessment of the normative-legal mechanisms regulating the jurisdictional framework for safeguarding the ontological prerogatives of the individual. The discourse surrounding the axiomatic categories of natural law remains at the forefront of profound scholarly investigations. However, contemporary geopolitical controversies, particularly the escalation of the Russo-Ukrainian military conflict, have exposed systemic lacunae within the existing human rights protection framework. The paradigmatic deficiencies of current jurisprudential algorithms are particularly evident in the domain of *jus pacis*, which serves as a determinant for the jurisdictional realisation of fundamental ontological rights, including *jus vitae*. Despite its explicit integration into the corpus of international legal regulations, this concept predominantly retains a declarative nature, highlighting the dissonance between its normative postulation and the practical functionality of human rights protection mechanisms amid escalating global destabilisation.

Literature review

The analysis of Ukraine's international security cooperation in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war is an important topic of contemporary research covering legal, military-strategic and geopolitical aspects. Due to the transformation of the global security system and the growing international threats, special attention is paid to Ukraine's role in the regional and global security architecture. The literature review includes an analysis of scientific works on Ukraine's international cooperation with NATO, the European Union, the UN and other international organizations, and studies of the impact of war on international legal mechanisms for ensuring security.

Melling¹ analyzes the UN General Assembly resolution "Uniting for Peace" as a tool to counteract the UN Security Council's blocking of Russia's aggression against Ukraine, pointing out its importance for international law. Strelbizka and Strelbizkyi² examine the international legal regulation of Ukraine's energy and nuclear security in times of war, focusing on the threats posed by the seizure of the Zaporizhzhia NPP. Zhou et al.³ examine the impact of war on global food and energy security, in particular through the disruption of supply chains and rising commodity prices. Hilde et al.⁴ analyze the impact of the war on the security situation in the Arctic, in particular on relations between Russia and Western countries in military and economic terms. Cull⁵ examines the issue of Ukraine's reputational security and its positioning in the international media, considering information warfare as one of the key fronts of the current conflict.

¹ G. Melling, "Evaluating the persisting relevance of the uniting for peace resolution for the maintenance of international peace and security: Russia's invasion of Ukraine and security council resolution 2623, (2022)", *International and Comparative Law Review*, Vol. 23, No. 1 (2023), pp. 256–272. <https://doi.org/10.2478/iclr-2023-0011>

² L. Strelbizka and M. Strelbizkyi, "International legal regulation of ensuring energy and nuclear security of Ukraine during war", *Information and law*, Vol. 1, No. 44 (2023), pp. 177–189. <https://doi.org/10.37750/2616-6798.2023.Vol. 1, No. 44.287782>

³ X. Y. Zhou, G. Lu, Z. Xu, X. Yan, S. T. Khu, J. Yang and J. Zhao, "Influence of Russia-Ukraine war on the global energy and food security", *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, Vol. 188 (2023), 106657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106657>

⁴ P. S. Hilde, F. Ohnishi and M. Petersson, "Cold winds in the north: Three perspectives on the impact of Russia's war in Ukraine on security and international relations in the Arctic", *Polar Science*, Vol. 41 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2024.101050>

⁵ N. J. Cull, "The war for Ukraine: Reputational security and media disruption", *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, Vol. 19, No. 2 (2023), pp. 195–199. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41254-022-00281-3>

Trypolska and Riabchyn⁶ assess the financing of renewable energy in Ukraine and the role of international partners in reducing dependence on Russian energy. Dyson et al.⁷ analyze the impact of the war on global food supply chains and measures to increase their resilience in the future. Rafols⁸ examines UN mechanisms in the context of Russia's aggression against Ukraine, pointing out the limited effectiveness of international law in modern armed conflicts. Shapoval and Nastyuk⁹ study the administrative and legal mechanisms for ensuring Ukraine's national security in the light of international experience. Smith and Dawson¹⁰ analyze neorealist approaches to understanding the war in Ukraine, especially in the context of global rivalry between the United States and Russia.

Matviienko and Petushkova¹¹ explore the EU's concept of cyber diplomacy and its potential application to Ukraine, which is relevant in light of hybrid warfare. Horovenko¹² examines international security alliances as tools for protecting fundamental human rights in the context of military conflict. Yaremko et al.¹³ conduct an archetypal analysis of the current state of Ukraine's international security, identifying key challenges and trends. Turchak et al.¹⁴ reveal the legal aspects of international military cooperation of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in 2014–2023, which allows to

⁶ G. Trypolska and O. Riabchyn, "Experience and prospects of financing renewable energy projects in Ukraine", *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, Vol. 12, No. 1 (2022), pp. 134–143. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijee.11999>

⁷ E. Dyson, R. Helbig, T. Avermaete, K. Halliwell, P. C. Calder, L. R. Brown, J. Ingram, et al., "Impacts of the Ukraine–Russia conflict on the global food supply chain and building future resilience", *EuroChoices*, Vol. 22, No. 1 (2023), pp. 14–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1746-692X.12380>

⁸ X. P. Rafols, "The war in Ukraine, the United Nations and international law: Some unsustainable systemic certainties", *Revista Electronica de Estudios Internacionales*, Vol. 2022, No. 43 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.17103/reei.43.08>

⁹ R. V. Shapoval and V. Y. Nastyuk, "International expertise in administrative legal support of national security in Ukraine", *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, Vol. 9, No. 36 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2016/v9i36/102031>

¹⁰ N. R. Smith and G. Dawson, "Mearsheimer, realism, and the Ukraine war", *Analyse und Kritik*, Vol. 44, No. 2 (2022), pp. 175–200. <https://doi.org/10.1515/auk-2022-2023>

¹¹ V. Matviienko and H. Petushkova, "Cyber diplomacy in the European Union: The Estonian cyber diplomacy model and the experience of Ukraine", *Diplomatic Ukraine*, Vol. XXIV (2023), pp. 696–708. <https://doi.org/10.37837/2707-7683-2023-37>

¹² S. Horovenko, "Institutionalized international security alliances: Defending fundamental human rights", *Uzhhorod National University Herald. Series: Law*, Vol. 3, No. 75 (2023), pp. 234–240. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2307-3322.2022.75.3.38>

¹³ I. Yaremko, Y. Mazur, V. Kharkovska and U. Lukashevskaya, "Archetypal analysis of the current state of international security of Ukraine", *Path of Science*, Vol. 6, No. 10 (2020), pp. 2023–2031. <https://doi.org/10.22178/pos.63-5>

¹⁴ I. Yaremko, Y. Mazur, V. Kharkovska and U. Lukashevskaya, "Archetypal analysis of the current state of international security of Ukraine", *Path of Science*, Vol. 6, No. 10 (2020), pp. 2023–2031. <https://doi.org/10.22178/pos.63-5>

trace its evolution and regulatory consolidation. Melling¹⁵ emphasizes the importance of reforming the international security system to adequately respond to the threats posed by the war in Ukraine.

Smith and Dawson¹⁶ analyze how political realism approaches explain the behavior of key geopolitical players in war. Zhou et al.¹⁷ examine the resilience of the global energy system under the influence of the Russian-Ukrainian war, emphasizing Ukraine's role as a transit state. Cull¹⁸ examines Ukraine's information security in light of manipulations and disinformation campaigns spread by Russia. Hilde et al.¹⁹ examine the consequences of the war for Europe's regional security, particularly in the area of military mobility. Dyson et al.²⁰ focus on the impact of the war on global food markets, which is a critical factor in the global economy.

Thus, the analysis of the literature shows that Ukraine's international security cooperation is a multidimensional process that covers legal, military, economic, and information aspects. The studies emphasize the need to adapt international legal mechanisms to new challenges associated with hybrid wars and the transformation of the global security order. Further research should focus on assessing the effectiveness of international initiatives to support Ukraine and on promising models of Ukraine's integration into the collective security system.

Materials and methods

The research procedure is based on a comprehensive approach to the study of Ukraine's international security cooperation in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. The analysis was carried out using an interdisciplinary approach, which allowed us to combine the political, legal, historical, international and security aspects of the research. The research covers the study of legal acts, strategic documents, international agreements, and decisions of international organizations related to the processes of Ukraine's integration into the global security system. Particular attention is paid to the assessment of structural reforms in the national security sector, Ukraine's military strategy and the evolution of its military and diplomatic relations with partners. A comparative analysis of changes in political narratives on Ukrainian security was conducted, the international community's response to threats posed by Russian aggression was studied, and prospects for the development of Ukraine's defense potential in cooperation with international security structures were outlined.

¹⁵ G. Melling, (2023).

¹⁶ N. R. Smith and G. Dawson, (2022).

¹⁷ X. Y. Zhou, G. Lu, Z. Xu, X. Yan, S. T. Khu, J. Yang and J. Zhao, (2023).

¹⁸ N. J. Cull, (2023).

¹⁹ P. S. Hilde, F. Ohnishi and M. Petersson, (2024).

²⁰ E. Dyson, R. Helbig, T. Avermaete, K. Halliwell, P. C. Calder, L. R. Brown, J. Ingram, et al., (2023).

The period under study covers 2014–2024, which is due to key historical events that had a direct impact on the security situation in Ukraine. The starting point of the sample was 2014, when the Revolution of Dignity resulted in a fundamental political shift that led to a change in the strategic course of the state, in particular, the rejection of non-aligned status and the definition of Euro-Atlantic integration as a priority direction of foreign policy. It was at this time that Russia's active military aggression began, with the annexation of Crimea and the incitement of an armed conflict in eastern Ukraine, which dramatically changed the format of Ukraine's international military and political cooperation. The period since 2022 has been a point of large-scale military escalation, which has led to a radical transformation of Ukraine's security policy, the expansion of military support from Western partners, the signing of a number of strategic agreements, the institutionalization of international assistance, and the active reform of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. The study used up-to-date sources for the entire period, which allowed us to trace the evolution of Ukraine's international security cooperation in the context of active hostilities and global changes in the international security system.

The research methodology is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis, which allows for a comprehensive study of the topic. The method of content analysis was used to assess international treaties, security agreements, strategic partnership programs and national regulations governing defense and international cooperation. The method of political and legal analysis was used to identify changes in the legislative and regulatory framework of Ukraine governing its participation in international security initiatives. The comparative method made it possible to assess the difference between the models of Ukraine's security cooperation before 2014 and after the beginning of Russia's armed aggression, to trace changes in the military and political positioning of the state within NATO, the EU and other defense alliances. To analyze the geopolitical situation and the international context, the method of geostrategic analysis was applied, which made it possible to determine the dynamics of Ukraine's relations with major international players, to assess their decisions to provide military, financial and political support. An important part of the methodology is the application of the scenario analysis method, which allows modeling potential options for the development of Ukraine's international security environment, depending on the evolution of the conflict and changes in the international situation.

The proposed research methodology is based on a systematic analysis of Ukraine's national and international security policy through the prism of its political, legal and geostrategic transformations. The use of a wide range of scientific methods allows us to describe the current state of Ukraine's international cooperation and predict possible scenarios for its further development, which is important for the development of future national security strategies and the country's integration into the Euro-Atlantic security system.

2: LEGISLATIVE INITIATIVES AS A RESPONSE TO RUSSIAN AGGRESSION

The development of Ukraine's international security cooperation has gained strategic importance since the beginning of Russian aggression in 2014. The rejection of the non-alignment policy and the direction of foreign policy towards Euro-Atlantic integration were enshrined in relevant legislative acts, such as the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Laws of Ukraine on Ukraine's Rejection of the Non-Alignment Policy"²¹. In 2015, the Agreement between the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine and NATO on the Status of the NATO Representation in Ukraine was signed, which was a key step in strengthening institutional cooperation²². Further development of the partnership included the adoption of Annual National Programs under the auspices of the NATO-Ukraine Commission aimed at reforming the security sector in line with Alliance standards²³.

In order to achieve interoperability of the Armed Forces of Ukraine with NATO structures, the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Laws of Ukraine on Military Standards" was adopted in 2019²⁴. This was facilitated by the introduction of NATO standards in the system of training military units and management of defense processes. An important step was the granting of NATO's Enhanced Opportunities Partner status to Ukraine in 2020, which provided Ukraine with access to the Alliance's advanced technologies and in-depth cooperation in the security sector²⁵.

2-1: STRENGTHENING PARTNERSHIPS

In 2022, in response to Russia's full-scale invasion, Ukraine applied for accelerated accession to NATO²⁶. This decision reflects the strategic course of the state, which is enshrined in the Constitution of Ukraine²⁷. An important milestone was

²¹ "Law of Ukraine "On amendments to some laws of Ukraine regarding the renunciation of Ukraine's non-aligned policy": Law No. 35-VIII", *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2014). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/35-19#Text>

²² "Agreement between the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine and NATO on the status of the NATO representation in Ukraine", *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2015). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/950_033

²³ President of Ukraine, "On the annual national programs under the aegis of the Ukraine-NATO commission: Presidential decree No. 547/2016", *Official Gazette of Ukraine*, (2016). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/547/2016>

²⁴ "Law of Ukraine "On amendments to the Constitution of Ukraine regarding the strategic course of the state for acquiring full membership in the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization": Law No. 2680-VIII", *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2019). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2680-19>

²⁵ "Memorandum of understanding between the Government of Ukraine and the NATO communications and information agency regarding cooperation in consultation, command, control, intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance within the NATO "partnership for peace" program", *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2022). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/950_001-22

²⁶ "Ukraine applies for accelerated NATO membership – Zelensky", *Militarnyi*, (2022). <https://mil.in.ua/uk/news/ukrayina-podaye-zayavku-na-pryshvydshenyj-vstup-do-nato-zelenskyj>

²⁷ *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2019).

the establishment of the NATO-Ukraine Council in 2023, which replaced the previous format of cooperation – the NATO-Ukraine Commission²⁸. At the same time, the Vilnius Summit decided to transform the Comprehensive Assistance Package into a multi-year program to support the reform of Ukraine’s defense sector.

The development of strategic partnership with the EU plays a crucial role in ensuring Ukraine’s defense capability. In 2014, Ukraine signed the Association Agreement with the EU, which consolidated its European integration course²⁹. Further cooperation included the signing in 2022 of a Memorandum between the Government of Ukraine and the European Defense Agency on military-technical cooperation³⁰. In 2024, a long-term security agreement was signed between Ukraine and the EU, which provides for support in the military-industrial complex, cybersecurity, and intelligence sharing³¹.

Table 1 shows the main directions of Ukraine’s international security cooperation.

Table 1. Main directions of Ukraine’s international security cooperation

Areas of cooperation	Organization/ Partner	Main achievements
Interaction with NATO	NATO	Granting EOP status, establishing the NATO-Ukraine Council
Military standards	NATO	Implementation of STANAG, adaptation of training programs
European security	EU	Defense cooperation agreement, cybersecurity
Bilateral alliances	USA, UK	Arms transfers, military training

²⁸ “Relations with Ukraine. North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO)”, *NATO official website*, (2024). <https://www.nato.int/cps/uk/natohq/index.htm>

²⁹ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, (2014).

³⁰ “Technical agreement No. 2023:01 on sponsorship of Ukraine’s ministry of defense as a guest partner mission in CFBLNet: Agreement No. 2023”, *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2024). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/950_001-24

³¹ President of Ukraine, “Joint security commitments between Ukraine and the European Union”, *Official website of the president of Ukraine*, (2024). <https://www.president.gov.ua/news/spilni-bezpekovi-zobov'язannya-mizh-ukrayinoyu-ta-yevropejsk-91801>

Enhanced military assistance	NATO partner countries	Multi-year military support packages
------------------------------	------------------------	--------------------------------------

Source: developed by the authors

2-2: SECURITY AND MILITARY COOPERATION LANDSCAPE

An important element of international military cooperation is the adoption of strategic documents such as the National Security Strategy of Ukraine³² and the Strategic Defense Bulletin of Ukraine³³. They define priorities for integration into NATO and the EU, defense sector reform, and strengthening the state's resilience to external threats.

Bilateral agreements with the United States, the United Kingdom, Poland, and other countries play a key role in security cooperation. In particular, significant military assistance is provided under defense support programs, such as the US Lend-Lease Act. The signing of the Technical Agreement between the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine and the NATO Communications and Information Agency in 2024 allowed for the modernization of the Armed Forces' communication systems³⁴.

Further expansion of Ukraine's international military cooperation will depend on progress in security sector reform, fulfillment of NATO criteria, and political support from partners. Ukraine's involvement in new defense initiatives, such as the NATO Support and Training Assistance Program (NSATU), is an important step in strengthening its defense capabilities³⁵. Given Ukraine's strategic importance in the European security architecture, the key task remains to ensure the effective implementation of international agreements and the integration of Ukrainian defense structures into the Euro-Atlantic security system.

Ukraine continues to strengthen its position in the international security space by integrating into the collective security system and expanding military and technical cooperation with partners. An important aspect of this process is the adaptation of the national defense policy to current challenges and threats, which includes reforming the Armed Forces, developing the defense industry and increasing the level of interoperability with NATO countries. Ukraine is focusing its efforts on achieving

³² President of Ukraine, "Decree on the national security strategy of Ukraine: Presidential decree No. 392/2020", Official Gazette of Ukraine, (2020). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/392/2020>

³³ President of Ukraine, "Decree on the strategic defense bulletin of Ukraine: Presidential decree No. 473/2021", Official Gazette of Ukraine, (2021). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/473/2021>

³⁴ "NATO summit in Washington: Heads of state and government of the North Atlantic Council participated in the meeting on the 75th anniversary of NATO", *Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2024). <https://www.rada.gov.ua/news/razom/251552.html>

³⁵ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, (2024).

strategic autonomy in the security sector, which involves developing its own military-industrial complex, implementing NATO standards, and creating effective mechanisms for rapid response to crisis situations³⁶. The state is actively involved in international peacekeeping and military missions, which contributes to its image as a reliable partner on the world stage.

An important element of international security cooperation is Ukraine's participation in multilateral defense initiatives³⁷, ³⁸. In particular, Ukraine actively cooperates with the Baltic states, Poland, Romania, and other partners in regional security formats, such as the Lublin Triangle and the Three Seas Initiative. These formats of cooperation allow for the creation of effective mechanisms for joint response to potential threats, ensuring prompt intelligence sharing, coordination of military exercises, and strengthening the region's defense capabilities. Ukraine is expanding cooperation with the European Defense Agency, which opens up new opportunities in the development of advanced military technologies and modernization of defense infrastructure.

3: IMPLICATIONS FOR SECURITY SECTOR OF UKRAINE

One of the key tasks in the security sector is to adapt Ukraine's defense sector to NATO standards, including structural reforms, digitalization of management processes, and introduction of new technologies in the military sphere. Particular attention is paid to the development of cybersecurity, as modern wars are fought on the battlefield and in the digital space. Ukraine has already created a number of strategic cyber defense centers that actively cooperate with the relevant EU and NATO structures. The country is expanding its cooperation in the field of artificial intelligence and unmanned technologies, which can significantly improve the efficiency of intelligence, surveillance, and operational management of military operations.

The development of Ukraine's defense industry is an important aspect of its military and strategic autonomy. Thanks to international partners, the country has been able to modernize its production facilities and expand the production of modern military equipment. Investments in the military-industrial complex allow for the development of the latest weapons adapted to modern combat conditions. In particular, joint projects with NATO countries contribute to the production of armored vehicles, air defense systems, and modern communications equipment. Ukraine is actively developing the defense and space sector, which involves cooperation with international companies in

³⁶ I. Lyutiy, Y. Petlenko and N. Drozd, "The importance of openness and transparency in the budget process in the defense and security sector of Ukraine", *Financial and Credit Activity: Problems of Theory and Practice*, Vol. 6, No. 47 (2022), pp. 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptop.6.47.2022.3900>

³⁷ "Roadmap for strategic communications partnership between the national security and defense council of Ukraine and the NATO international secretariat", *Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine*, (2015). http://mfa.gov.ua/mediafiles/sites/nato/files/Roadmap_Ukr.pdf

³⁸ "Ukraine signed an updated edition of the roadmap on defense and technical cooperation", *Mission of Ukraine to NATO*, (2019). <https://nato.mfa.gov.ua/news/76590-ukrajina-pidpisala-onovlenu-redakciju-dorozhnyoji-karti-ukrajina-nato-z-oboronno-tehnichnogo-spivrobotnictva>

the field of satellite technology and electronic warfare. The structure of Ukraine's international security cooperation is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of Ukraine's international security cooperation

Source: developed by the authors

3-1: UKRAINE'S INTERNATIONAL SECURITY COOPERATION: OVERALL CONCERNS

In recent years, specialized units have been created to monitor, prevent, and neutralize cyberattacks targeting both government institutions and critical infrastructure. In cooperation with the EU and NATO, Ukraine is implementing comprehensive cybersecurity programs, including the use of artificial intelligence to analyze threats, the creation of rapid response centers, and the development of a national cybersecurity system capable of ensuring the security of data and information systems. Efforts are underway to integrate digital solutions into the military sector, which will optimize the command and control of military operations, increasing the effectiveness of management at the strategic level.

Participation in joint military exercises and maneuvers plays a special role in Ukraine's international security cooperation. Regular exercises with NATO countries, such as Rapid Trident, Sea Breeze, and Combined Resolve, allow to improve the level of combat training of the Ukrainian military, test interoperability with partner armies, and practice joint tactical actions. Particular importance is attached to personnel training, which includes training under NATO programs and training with foreign instructors. This makes it possible to adapt the Armed Forces to modern challenges and integrate them into the overall system of collective security.

Prospects for Ukraine's international security cooperation are determined by external factors, such as political support from partners and changes in the geopolitical context, and internal reforms in the defense and national security sectors. Further integration into NATO structures, expanding cooperation in military and technical development, and strengthening cybersecurity remain key priorities. Active cooperation with partners to create new mechanisms to deter threats, in particular through

participation in European defense initiatives, will strengthen Ukraine's position as a strategic partner in the security sector.

4: DISCUSSION

4-1: A DISCOURSE OF LIBERAL INTERVENTIONISM, NATIONAL SECURITY SYSTEM, AND INTERNATIONAL SECURITY AGREEMENTS

The results confirm the findings presented in the current scientific literature on the importance of Ukraine's international security cooperation and its evolution in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. Geis and Schröder³⁹ emphasize the paradigm shift of liberal interventionism in light of Russia's aggression against Ukraine, which is in line with our findings on the need for Ukraine's deeper integration into the collective security system. In turn, Levytska et al.⁴⁰ emphasize the importance of preserving the economic potential of critical infrastructure, which is consistent with our analysis of international support for rebuilding Ukraine's defense and security sector. The study by Shapovalov⁴¹ demonstrates that international military cooperation is an important element of Ukraine's national security system, which confirms our conclusions about its strategic importance in the wartime and post-war period.

Another study, presented by Fayl et al.⁴², examines international security agreements signed in connection with the war in Ukraine, which confirms our thesis about the gradual transformation of the global security order. The authors pay special attention to the issues of legal guarantees of security, which coincides with our conclusions about the need to revise international mechanisms for deterring aggression. At the same time, the study by Unggul Wicaksana Prakasa et al.⁴³ analyzes the impact of war on the aviation sector, emphasizing the security challenges arising from violations of international airspace agreements. This aspect correlates with our results, which demonstrate a significant impact of war on the global security system. In turn, Drażkiewicz et al.⁴⁴ emphasize the need for an interdisciplinary approach to studying

³⁹ A. Geis and U. Schröder, "The Russian war against Ukraine and its implications for the future of liberal interventionism", *Politics and Governance*, Vol. 12 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.7348>

⁴⁰ S. Levytska, O. Osadcha and L. Tykhonchuk, "Security of economic potential for critical infrastructure subjects", *Scientific Notes of Ostroh Academy National University, "Economics" Series*, Vol. 31, No. 59 (2023), pp. 4–12. [https://doi.org/10.25264/2311-5149-2023-31\(59\)-4-12](https://doi.org/10.25264/2311-5149-2023-31(59)-4-12)

⁴¹ H. M. Shapovalov, (2022).

⁴² V. Fayl, U. Hentaller, G. Fayl, D. H. Price and I. Grga, "International security agreement - war in Ukraine", *SSRN Electronic Journal*, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4236757>

⁴³ S. Unggul Wicaksana Prakasa, A. Wijayanti, A. Hariri and L. Yustitiningtyas, "The effect of Russia-Ukraine war on international aviation sectors", *KnE Social Sciences*, (2022), pp. 572–581. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v7i15.12132>

⁴⁴ E. Drażkiewicz, N. Tchernalykh, V. Artiukh, K. Follis, I. Käihkö, O. Fedjuk et al., "Forum: Russia's invasion of Ukraine", *Social Anthropology*, Vol. 31, No. 2 (2023), pp. 119–156. <https://www.berghahnjournals.com/view/journals/saas/31/2/saas310209.xml>

the effects of war, which is consistent with our use of a comprehensive method of security risk analysis.

4-2: ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES DISCUSSIONS

The study by Hryhorczuk et al.⁴⁵ emphasizes the environmental consequences of war and their impact on public health, which demonstrates the broader context of security threats than the purely military aspect. In our study, this aspect is considered through the prism of international assistance to Ukraine in the area of eliminating environmental disasters caused by the war. The study by Caprile⁴⁶, which analyzes the effects of war on food security, is relevant and confirms our results on the complex nature of security challenges. Turchak et al.⁴⁷ focus on the legal aspects of international military cooperation, which is consistent with our findings on the need to modernize the security regulatory framework.

Thus, the results of the study are confirmed by modern scientific works that emphasize the importance of adapting the international security system to modern challenges and the need to expand legal mechanisms for guaranteeing security. Further research should focus on analyzing the effectiveness of specific mechanisms of international support for Ukraine and identifying strategies that can ensure long-term stability in the region.

CONCLUSION

5

Over the past decade, Ukraine's international security cooperation has undergone dramatic transformations due to the changing geopolitical situation and escalation of military aggression by the Russian Federation. Since 2014, Ukraine has carried out a comprehensive restructuring of its security strategy, which included the abandonment of its non-aligned status, deepening cooperation with NATO and the European Union, and a large-scale reform of the Armed Forces to achieve interoperability with NATO member states. The implementation of strategic defense programs, the introduction of Euro-Atlantic standards in the military sphere, and active involvement in international military exercises have contributed to strengthening Ukraine's defense capabilities and enhancing its role in the regional security system. A special role in strengthening international support was played by the security agreements signed in 2022–2024 with

⁴⁵ D. Hryhorczuk, B. S. Levy, M. Prodanchuk, O. Kravchuk, N. Bubalo, A. Hryhorczuk and T. B. Erickson, "The environmental health impacts of Russia's war on Ukraine", *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*, Vol. 19 (2024), p. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12995-023-00398-y>

⁴⁶ A. Caprile, "Russia's war on Ukraine: Impact on food security and EU response. European Parliamentary Research Service", *Think Tank European Parliament*, (2022). <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank>

⁴⁷ O. V. Turchak, Y. V. Burakov and A. V. Posokhova, (2023).

the EU and G7 countries, which define long-term mechanisms of military, financial and technological support.

At the same time, further development of Ukraine's international security cooperation requires a systematic approach to expanding defense partnerships, modernizing the military-industrial complex, and integrating advanced defense technologies. An important factor is the continued reform of the security sector in accordance with NATO standards, including the digitalization of military management, the development of cybersecurity, and the enhancement of critical infrastructure resilience. Successful implementation of these processes will help strengthen Ukraine's defense capabilities, expand its strategic partnership in the international security environment, and create preconditions for further integration into the Euro-Atlantic space.

References

1. Caprile, A. (2022). Russia's war on Ukraine: Impact on food security and EU response. *European Parliamentary Research Service*, (April), 1–2. <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank>
2. Cull, N. J. (2023). The war for Ukraine: Reputational security and media disruption. *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, 19(2), 195–199. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41254-022-00281-3>
3. Drażkiewicz, E., Tchermalykh, N., Artiukh, V., Follis, K., Käihkö, I., Fedjuk, O., ... Ivancheva, M. (2023). Forum: Russia's invasion of Ukraine. *Social Anthropology/Anthropologie Sociale*, 31(2), 119–156. <https://www.berghahnjournals.com/view/journals/saas/31/2/saas310209.xml>
4. Dyson, E., Helbig, R., Avermaete, T., Halliwell, K., Calder, P. C., Brown, L. R., Ingram, J., ..., Boyle, N. (2023, April 1). *Impacts of the Ukraine–Russia conflict on the global food supply chain and building future resilience*. EuroChoices. John Wiley and Sons Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1746-692X.12380>
5. European Pravda (2015). Minister of Defense approved the plan for the transition of the Armed Forces of Ukraine to NATO standards. *European Pravda*. <https://www.euointegration.com.ua/news/2015/11/26/7041375>
6. Fayl V. Hentaller, U., Fayl, G., Price, D. H., & Grga, I. (2022). International security agreement - war in Ukraine. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4236757>
7. Geis, A., & Schröder, U. (2024). The Russian war against Ukraine and its implications for the future of liberal interventionism. *Politics and Governance*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.7348>

8. Government of Ukraine & NATO (2015). Agreement between the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine and NATO on the status of the NATO representation in Ukraine. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/950_033
9. Government of Ukraine & NATO (2022). Memorandum of understanding between the Government of Ukraine and the NATO communications and information agency regarding cooperation in consultation, command, control, intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance within the NATO “partnership for peace” program. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/950_001-22
10. Hilde, P. S., Ohnishi, F., & Petersson, M. (2024). Cold winds in the north: Three perspectives on the impact of Russia’s war in Ukraine on security and international relations in the Arctic. *Polar Science*, 41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2024.101050>
11. Horovenko, S. (2023). Institutionalized international security alliances: Defending fundamental human rights. *Uzhhorod National University Herald. Series: Law*, 3(75), 234–240. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2307-3322.2022.75.3.38>
12. Hryhorczuk, D., Levy, B. S., Prodanchuk, M., Kravchuk, O., Bubalo, N., Hryhorczuk, A., & Erickson, T. B. (2024, December 1). The environmental health impacts of Russia’s war on Ukraine. *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*. BioMed Central Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12995-023-00398-y>
13. Levytska, S., Osadcha, O., & Tykhonchuk, L. (2023). Security of economic potential for critical infrastructure subjects. *Scientific Notes of Ostroh Academy National University, “Economics” Series*, 1(31), 4–12. [https://doi.org/10.25264/2311-5149-2023-31\(59\)-4-12](https://doi.org/10.25264/2311-5149-2023-31(59)-4-12)
14. Lukhtan, A. I. (2018). *International military cooperation of Ukraine (1991–2013): Ph.D. dissertation in historical sciences*. Kyiv. <https://nuou.org.ua/assets/dissertations/autoref/avtoref-luhtan.pdf>
15. Lyutiy, I., Petlenko, Y., & Drozd, N. (2022). The importance of openness and transparency in the budget process in the defense and security sector of Ukraine. *Financial and Credit Activity: Problems of Theory and Practice*, 6(47), 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptp.6.47.2022.3900>
16. Matviienko, V., & Petushkova, H. (2023). Cyber diplomacy in the European Union: The Estonian cyber diplomacy model and the experience of Ukraine. *Diplomatic Ukraine*, (XXIV), 696–708. <https://doi.org/10.37837/2707-7683-2023-37>
17. Melling, G. (2023). Evaluating the persisting relevance of the uniting for peace resolution for the maintenance of international peace and security: Russia’s invasion of Ukraine and security council resolution 2623 (2022). *International and Comparative Law Review*, 23(1), 256–272. <https://doi.org/10.2478/iclr-2023-0011>
18. Militaryni. (2022). Ukraine applies for accelerated NATO membership – Zelensky. *Militaryni*. <https://mil.in.ua/uk/news/ukrayina-podaye-zayavku-na-pryshvydshenyjvstup-do-nato-zelenskyj>

19. Ministry of Defense of Ukraine & NATO. (2024). Technical agreement No. 2023:01 on sponsorship of Ukraine's ministry of defense as a guest partner mission in CFBLNet: Agreement No. 2023. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/950_001-24
20. Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine (2015). Roadmap for strategic communications partnership between the national security and defense council of Ukraine and the NATO international secretariat. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. http://mfa.gov.ua/mediafiles/sites/nato/files/Roadmap_Ukr.pdf
21. Mission of Ukraine to NATO (2019). *Ukraine signed an updated edition of the roadmap on defense and technical cooperation*. Mission of Ukraine to NATO. <https://nato.mfa.gov.ua/news/76590-ukrajina-pidpisala-onovlenu-redakciju-dorozhnyoji-karti-ukrajina-nato-z-oboronno-tehnicnogo-spivrobotnictva>
22. National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine (2014). Decision of the national security and defense council of Ukraine dated August 28, 2014, "On urgent measures to protect Ukraine and strengthen its defense capabilities": Presidential decree No. 744/2014. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/744/2014>
23. NATO official website (2024). *Relations with Ukraine*. North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). <https://www.nato.int/cps/uk/natohq/index.htm>
24. President of Ukraine (2009). Decree on the annual national program of cooperation between Ukraine and NATO: Presidential decree No. 298/2009. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/298/2009>
25. President of Ukraine (2015a). Decree on the strategy of national security of Ukraine: Presidential decree No. 287/2015. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/287/2015>
26. President of Ukraine (2015b). Decree on the new edition of the military doctrine of Ukraine: Presidential decree No. 555/2015. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/555/2015>
27. President of Ukraine. (2016). On the annual national programs under the aegis of the Ukraine-NATO commission: Presidential decree No. 547/2016. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/547/2016>
28. President of Ukraine. (2020). Decree on the national security strategy of Ukraine: Presidential decree No. 392/2020. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/392/2020>
29. President of Ukraine. (2021). Decree on the strategic defense bulletin of Ukraine: Presidential decree No. 473/2021. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/473/2021>

30. President of Ukraine. (2024). Joint security commitments between Ukraine and the European Union. *Official website of the president of Ukraine*. <https://www.president.gov.ua/news/spilni-bezpekovi-zoboviazannya-mizh-ukrayinoyu-ta-yevropejsk-91801>
31. Rafols, X. P. (2022). The war in Ukraine, the United Nations and international law: Some unsustainable systemic certainties. *Revista Electronica de Estudios Internacionales*, 2022(43). <https://doi.org/10.17103/reei.43.08>
32. Shapoval, R. V., & Nastyuk, V. Y. (2016). International expertise in administrative legal support of national security in Ukraine. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(36). <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2016/v9i36/102031>
33. Shapovalov, H. M. (2022). International military cooperation in the national security system. *Investments: Practice and Experience*, 22, 110–115. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32702/2306-6814.2022.22.110>
34. Smith, N. R., & Dawson, G. (2022). Mearsheimer, realism, and the Ukraine war. *Analyse und Kritik*, 44(2), 175–200. <https://doi.org/10.1515/auk-2022-2023>
35. Strelbizka, L., & Strelbizkyi, M. (2023). International legal regulation of ensuring energy and nuclear security of Ukraine during war. *Information and law*, 1(44), 177–189. [https://doi.org/10.37750/2616-6798.2023.1\(44\).287782](https://doi.org/10.37750/2616-6798.2023.1(44).287782)
36. Trypolska, G., & Riabchyn, O. (2022). Experience and prospects of financing renewable energy projects in Ukraine. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 12(1), 134–143. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijep.11999>
37. Turchak, O. V., Burakov, Y. V., & Posokhova, A. V. (2023). Legal basis of international military cooperation of the armed forces of Ukraine during the Russian-Ukrainian war (2014-2023). *Analytical and comparative jurisprudence*, 432–436. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2788-6018.2023.03.78>
38. Unggul Wicaksana Prakasa, S., Wijayanti, A., Hariri, A., & Yustitiningtyas, L. (2022). *The effect of Russia--Ukraine war on international aviation sectors*. KnE Social Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v7i15.12132>
39. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (2014). Law of Ukraine "On amendments to some laws of Ukraine regarding the renunciation of Ukraine's non-aligned policy": Law No. 35-VIII. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/35-19#Text>
40. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (2019). Law of Ukraine "On amendments to the Constitution of Ukraine regarding the strategic course of the state for acquiring full membership in the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization": Law No. 2680-VIII. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2680-19>
41. Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (2024). NATO summit in Washington: Heads of state and government of the North Atlantic Council participated in the meeting on the 75th anniversary of NATO. *Official Gazette of Ukraine*. <https://www.rada.gov.ua/news/razom/251552.html>

42. Yaremko, I., Mazur, Y., Karkovska, V., Lukashyvska, U. (2020). Archetypal analysis of the current state of international security of Ukraine. *Path of Science*, 6(10), 2023–2031. <https://doi.org/10.22178/pos.63-5>
43. Zhou, X. Y., Lu, G., Xu, Z., Yan, X., Khu, S. T., Yang, J., & Zhao, J. (2023). Influence of Russia-Ukraine war on the global energy and food security. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106657>

